

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Resource Efficient Federated LoRaWAN Architecture for Far-Edge IoT Applications

ANNA TRIANTAFYLLOU¹, ILIAS SINIOSGLOU^{1,2},
VASILEIOS ARGYRIOU³, (Member, IEEE),
SOTIRIOS K. GOUDOS⁴, (Senior Member, IEEE),
GEORGIOS TH. PAPADOPOULOS⁵, (Member, IEEE),
KONSTANTINOS PANITSIDIS⁶, AND
PANAGIOTIS SARIGIANNIDIS^{1,2}, (Member, IEEE)

¹Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, 501 00 Kozani, Greece

²MetaMind Innovations P.C., 501 00 Kozani, Greece

³Department of Networks and Digital Media, Kingston University London, KT1 2EE London, U.K.

⁴Physics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 541 24 Thessaloniki, Greece

⁵Department of Informatics and Telematics, Harokopio University of Athens, 176 76 Athens, Greece

⁶Department of Management Science and Technology, University of Western Macedonia, 501 00 Kozani, Greece

Corresponding author: Sotirios K. Goudos (sgoudo@physics.auth.gr)

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ABSTRACT This study introduces an innovative, resource-efficient architecture that incorporates advanced technologies to create a lightweight, flexible, and scalable framework for remote and limited data collecting and processing in next-generation Internet of Things (IoT) applications. It specifically proposes an integrated Federated LoRaWAN (LoRa-FL) system that combines hierarchical, privacy-preserving Federated Learning (FL), Knowledge Distillation (KD), and a customised Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol, identified as FCA-LoRa, to address the significant limitations of LoRaWAN networks. These encompass strict duty cycle rules, restricted bandwidth, and energy limitations, elements that conventionally hinder the implementation of intelligent IoT devices in rural or isolated settings. The proposed architecture features a hierarchical FL approach enabling multi-tier Artificial Intelligence (AI) model aggregation across edge nodes, gateways, and a central server. The effectiveness of the proposed system is confirmed by two practical applications, smart agriculture and smart livestock farming, which exemplify standard situations for far-edge intelligence. The results indicate that the distilled model consistently attains over 90% packet delivery success, illustrating the architecture's capacity to provide scalable and energy-efficient intelligence at the edge. This research addresses a significant gap in previous studies that frequently examine FL, communication optimisation, and model compression independently. This study offers a comprehensive, implementable approach that tackles model scalability, and network-layer issues within a cohesive architecture, enhancing the practical implementation of AI-driven IoT deployments over LoRaWAN.

INDEX TERMS LoRaWAN, federated learning, knowledge distillation, Internet of Things, scheduling, architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's technological era, which is described by insurmountable information plurality and supported by

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cutting-edge technological advancements in communications, processing, and actuation, we see a clear paradigm shift to more decentralised infrastructures. Nowadays, these infrastructures enable expedited and precise information processing, resulting in a synthesis of distributed and decentralised data creation and processing centres. This

is particularly true for facilities with local preconditions, such as remote deployments or specialised actuation-oriented applications, including large-scale smart farming, unmanned surveillance (drones), weather stations, remote energy substations, and housing. The current technological advancement has facilitated applications to autonomously collect data and provide decision support, enabling a range of applications previously hindered by limitations such as the restricted energy supply, communication range, bandwidth, and processing power to manage the generated data.

Long Range Wide Area Networks (LoRaWAN) is a pivotal technology that facilitates such applications by offering low energy consumption, extensive area coverage, and low bit rates while maintaining enough throughput [1]. The distinct qualities differentiate Low-Power Wide-Area Networks (LPWANs) from a wireless WAN, which aims to connect individuals or enterprises and transmit larger volumes of data while consuming more power. LoRa has gained extensive adoption in Europe and the United States, functioning within the internationally accessible 868/915-MHz ISM bands. This technology can transmit data at 50 kbps and reach 15–30 km in rural areas with a 10-year battery life. Recent research has identified numerous LoRa challenges, mostly due to regulatory duty cycle constraints that limit device data packet transmission [2]. Although LoRaWAN technology offers low energy consumption via low-power, long-range communication lines, throughput may be hindered by packet collisions, an issue arising from LoRa's initial scheduling procedure. Packet transmission lengths are long, and collisions are likely to occur due to LoRa's physical layer's higher spreading factors and uncertain channel access. Towards dealing with these challenges, a unique Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol, designated FCA-LoRa, has been developed to improve reliability and minimise collisions in LoRa-based wide-area networks [3].

On the other hand, to handle the big informational load produced by such facilities, a clear paradigm shift has been underway, integrating artificial intelligence into such applications. This enables fast and accurate prediction of patterns from acquired data, providing informed and immediate decision support under deployment conditions. In most cases, where applications are centralized in the cloud or hosted in in-house deployments at localized processing centers with ample data, AI becomes a powerful, optimized, and well-informed tool [4]. However, this is not the case in remote and decentralized applications. In such environments, even though local data may be ample, it is often static and specific to the local context, which limits AI's ability to generalize effectively. AI performance suffers due to the lack of diverse and dynamic data [5], making it suboptimal. Furthermore, obtaining more diverse data from other sources is challenging due to difficulties in data transport and the numerous issues, such as security, privacy concerns, and resource constraints, associated with managing large datasets in remote conditions.

Federated Learning (FL) [6] is an innovative solution to the above-mentioned problem that has received great scientific and commercial interest. With FL, we can train models on decentralized data sources without the need to centralize sensitive information, thus addressing privacy concerns and regulatory restrictions [7]. In this article, we discuss the practical implications of FL, exploring how it affects LoRa-supported decentralised applications when compared to traditional centralized training methodologies. Of course, even with the ability to send only model weight updates, some models can reach the limits of the available LoRa bandwidth, creating a communication overhead. To tackle this, technologies like Knowledge Distillation (KD) can be leveraged, that refine the knowledge of AI models into smaller surrogates (student models) that are more lightweight and optimal for transfer, while showing advanced performance.

This article explores the advantages and applications resulting from the integration of LoRa-based communication, Federated Learning, and edge intelligence, with the objective of creating a lightweight, efficient, and flexible ecosystem for remote and limited data acquisition [8], [9], as well as a resilient processing platform for next-generation IoT applications [10]. This study presents an innovative LoRa-enabled architecture that incorporates a private-by-design, hierarchical federated learning system, specifically designed to facilitate intelligent inference in very resource-constrained edge contexts.

Several recent research have progressed the application of FL, model optimisation, and LoRa-based communication in IoT scenarios, nevertheless each addresses specific aspects of the broader challenges. Concentrating on FL and model personalisation, the distribution of learning across various data sources is examined while preserving privacy and improving generalisation. Studies such as [11] and [12] illustrate that FL can generate high-quality models from decentralised datasets, particularly in smart agriculture scenarios, and that KD can facilitate the adaptation of lightweight models for edge nodes. Nevertheless, these researches assess learning outcomes in isolation, ignoring the influence of network communication limits or hardware limitations. Likewise, the work in [13] implements federated learning in a LoRaWAN-based transportation context and presents strategies for managing noisy labels; however, it neglects model compression and channel-aware model distribution.

Regarding communication efficiency and MAC-layer optimisation, earlier research pertains to the transmission of data and model updates over limited networks such as LoRaWAN. Effective communication protocols are crucial for scaling federated learning in contexts with constrained bandwidth and stringent duty cycles. The work in [14] presents an asynchronous MAC method (FL-LoRaMAC) that minimises raw data transfer via compression; however, it does not provide a comprehensive architectural framework or coordination among federated layers. The study in [15]

presents a multi-agent reinforcement learning methodology aimed at enhancing QoS via adaptive radio parameter adjustment, but it fails to incorporate model efficiency or address hierarchical learning dynamics. These studies emphasise the necessity of optimising channel access and alleviating network congestion, although they fail to integrate FL and MAC-level coordination into a cohesive framework.

Moreover, recent research was focused on energy-efficient and edge-oriented IoT intelligence, a topic proven essential for implementing smart systems in power-limited, remote environments. The work in [16] uses KD to distil models, enhancing their suitability for edge inference, although it does not integrate FL or tackle model distribution. The work in [17] evaluates FL on LoRa mesh networks, providing a proof of concept but lacking in architectural rigour and MAC-layer integration. The study in [18] presents energy-aware client selection utilising game theory in FL; nevertheless, it neglects protocol-level efficiency and cross-layer communication. The work in [19] emphasises efficient object detection using downsampled image transmission via LoRa, showcasing compatibility with edge devices, but neglects collaborative learning techniques and network-level optimisations. The study in [20] proposes a KD-based federated fine-tuning approach using Low-Rank Adaptation and logit-level model-free FL to reduce communication and storage costs. However, it is network-agnostic and does not address MAC-layer or architectural constraints typical of LoRaWAN-based IoT systems.

On the contrary, our study tackles the shortcomings in these research domains by presenting a comprehensive architecture that integrates hierarchical FL, knowledge distillation, and a customised MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) [3]. This architecture is specifically engineered for LoRaWAN, addressing practical limitations such as restricted data speeds, strict duty cycle regulations, and the necessity for low-power functionality. It facilitates lightweight model transfer, reduces network congestion, and encourages collaborative learning among dispersed, resource-limited nodes—attributes not collectively realised in prior research.

Implementing such a system is particularly essential as IoT ecosystems rapidly spread into infrastructure-constrained contexts such as smart agriculture and animal management. These scenarios necessitate decentralised, energy-efficient, and privacy-preserving solutions capable of operating effectively without reliance on cloud infrastructure. The content of our work is noteworthy as it offers a cohesive, deployable solution that not only corresponds to the objectives of previous research but also enhances them by addressing critical architectural and practical obstacles to real-world edge intelligence via LoRaWAN. Unlike prior studies that primarily focus on demonstrating FL accuracy, our contribution lies in addressing the system-level and architectural challenges that arise when deploying FL in such constrained environments. While earlier research confirms that FL is technically viable in LoRaWAN settings, it often neglects the architectural coordination, energy-awareness,

and communication optimization necessary for real-world, large-scale IoT deployments. The value of our work lies not in improving FL accuracy per se, but in delivering a cohesive and resource-efficient framework that enables scalable, low-power, and practical FL deployments over LoRaWAN. Our simulation-based evaluation further supports the feasibility of this approach, providing a solid foundation for future real-world implementations.

These contributions collectively advance the state of the art by overcoming critical limits [21] in scalability, energy efficiency, and coordination in FL-based IoT installations, finally providing a holistic solution for practical applications such as smart agriculture and animal monitoring.

In summarising, the contributions of this article are:

- Introduction of a reference private-by-design Federated LoRaWAN architecture to support far-edge intelligence.
- Integration of a highly efficient LoRa protocol (FCA-LoRa) to support the FL implementation.
- Exploration of KD as a medium for lightweight and optimised AI model transference over LoRa.
- Definition of a resource-efficient FL model distribution scheme over LoRaWAN focused on system-level practicality rather than accuracy gains.
- Study of two unique and real-world test cases for the developed system.
- Achieving a consistent throughput exceeding 90% for AI model transfer in LoRa-based networks.

II. RELATED WORK

Various research initiatives have been proposed to integrate AI with LoRa technology. Nonetheless, due to the fact that machine learning and LoRa-based IoT applications have developed separately, the integration of machine learning with networked LoRa connections remains inadequately comprehended.

In 2021, Kumari et al. [16] suggested a Knowledge Distillation-based Transportation (KDT) system that gathered sensory data from an intelligent transportation network, used LoRa for low-energy decision data communication, and applied a compressed deep learning model via knowledge distillation to enable inference on limited-resource devices. Although this method emphasised mostly single decision-making without more architectural integration or multi-level learning coordination, it showed encouraging outcomes by balancing energy economy and model accuracy through a game-theoretic selection of student models and coding rates. Building on this foundation, the current study presents a more thorough and scalable approach by including knowledge distillation inside a hierarchical Federated Learning architecture over a LoRaWAN backbone. Unlike the preceding KDT system, which ran in a single-node, single-model environment, the suggested Federated LoRaWAN architecture allows cooperative learning across distributed IoT devices, maintaining data privacy while reducing communication cost. Furthermore, it provides an

improved Medium Access Control layer (FCA-LoRa) [3] to reduce packet collisions and increase throughput, a topic not addressed in the 2021 research. The suggested system provides scalable, adaptable, and energy-aware intelligence at the far edge by means of hierarchical FL, KD, and FCA-LoRa, hence attaining consistent model transfer performance and practical relevance in areas including smart agriculture and animal husbandry.

In 2022, Jindal et al. [19] suggested an energy-efficient object identification system using LoRa-based communication across edge computing nodes, where duties like image capture, compression, and inference were spread among devices including Raspberry Pi, Jetson Nano, and Coral DevBoard. Their method emphasised reducing power utilisation by sending downsampled images over LoRa and employing upsampling methods like bicubic interpolation and ESRGAN on edge devices before inference with deep learning models such as SSD-MobileNetV2. While maintaining reasonable degrees of model accuracy, the framework showed a significant drop in energy use—up to 1.2 watts during inference. Though the study mainly focusses on efficient picture transmission and local inference features, it provides an effective solution for low-power object recognition in limited settings. It overlooks collaborative learning across devices or model optimisation for scalable deployments. Our present work builds on this foundation to allow distributed, privacy-preserving model training over LoRaWAN-connected nodes by combining hierarchical federated learning with knowledge distillation methods. Moreover, it presents FCA-LoRa [3], a maximised MAC protocol that reduces packet collisions and enhances communication efficiency, an area not covered in the previous work. This integrated approach not only preserves energy efficiency and edge-device compatibility but also allows scalable, adaptive learning in actual smart agriculture and livestock environments, so bridging the gaps in coordination, model convergence, and communication-layer optimisation found in Jindal et al.'s design.

During 2023, the authors in [14] presented FL-LoRaMAC, a Federated Learning system designed for LoRa-based IoT networks. Their method showed how on-device training and asynchronous MAC protocols might greatly lower connection costs while maintaining data privacy and addressing the fundamental constraints of centralised machine learning in limited IoT environments. FL-LoRaMAC maintained high model performance while significantly lowering transmitted data volume by means of model trimming, principal component analysis, and a new SF allocation algorithm. Although FL-LoRaMAC is a significant improvement in privacy-preserving and communication-efficient on-device learning, it still mostly targets single-application use cases with flat federation structures and little regard for edge coordination or multi-tier model aggregation. Our study builds on this basis by presenting a hierarchically organised federated learning system run over a scalable LoRaWAN infrastructure, coupled with knowledge distillation methods and an improved MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) [3]. Unlike

FL-LoRaMAC, which mostly focusses on uplink/downlink communication in isolated devices, our work enables cooperative learning across resource-constrained devices in actual agricultural and pastoral settings, hence guaranteeing both energy efficiency and consistent model convergence. Our suggested approach closes important architectural and operational holes by merging hierarchical FL, model compression, and a collision-avoidance-aware MAC layer, hence advancing more strong, adaptive, and scalable edge intelligence.

Furthermore, the authors in [17] investigated the viability of running Federated Learning straight on microcontroller boards linked by a LoRa mesh network. Their system design included a dual-board architecture, with the Arduino Portenta H7 managing embedded machine learning duties and a TTGO-LORA32 board controlling LoRa-based connectivity. Their work showed the practical deployment of decentralised FL at the tiny edge by training a neural network for keyword spotting across distributed nodes without centralised aggregation, stressing on-device retraining, memory management, and communication dependability over limited LoRa links. Although this paper clearly demonstrated the possibility for embedded FL over LoRa mesh networks, its focus was restricted to static peer-to-peer model sharing and small-scale, mesh-specific implementations. By including knowledge distillation inside a hierarchically organised FL framework constructed on top of a LoRaWAN backbone, our present work expands these ideas in contrast to those of the past, hence enabling scalable and cooperative intelligence beyond mesh topologies. The addition of an optimised collision-aware MAC layer (FCA-LoRa) [3] also guarantees effective model exchange even in crowded network conditions, a difficulty not handled in the 2023 paper. The suggested system therefore not only preserves the embedded, low-power philosophy of previous work but also broadens its relevance to more general, real-world IoT applications like precision agriculture and livestock monitoring, where scalability, energy efficiency, and adaptive model generalisation are top priorities.

In addition, during 2023, Kumar et al. [13] proposed Fed-LoRa, a federated learning method meant for intelligent transport systems (ITS) running over LoRa-based communication networks. By use of a centroid-based similarity approach to identify participants with low-quality labels, their system tackled a fundamental problem in FL: handling incorrectly labelled data. Without increasing local datasets, these “inferior participants” subsequently got an ideally computed portion of well-annotated data from a central server to improve their model performance. By keeping communication efficiency through LoRa, Fed-LoRa showed robustness against noisy data and offered a privacy-preserving solution appropriate for distributed automotive situations. Although Fed-LoRa significantly strengthened FL under label noise and created efficient communication patterns over LoRa networks, its use remained concentrated on static ITS data types and it had no tools for controlling hierarchical model architectures or optimising low-power transmission outside

data transfer volume. Our current study builds on this by presenting a LoRaWAN-based hierarchical federated learning system that includes knowledge distillation enabling lightweight model deployment over limited edge devices. Furthermore, it improves MAC-layer performance with the FCA-LoRa protocol [3], directly tackling the scalability and collision issues not addressed in Fed-LoRa. Our suggested approach not only supports the label robustness emphasis of Fed-LoRa but also scales it for complicated, data-intensive applications in precision agriculture and livestock monitoring by means of energy-aware learning, real-time coordination, and cross-layer optimisation.

In light of experimenting with the employment of FL in trending LoRaWAN applications, a very recent study [18] suggested SusFL, an energy-aware FL framework particularly created for smart agriculture to solve energy sustainability issues in LoRaWAN-based Federated Learning settings. Based on mechanism design, their system presented a novel game-theoretic client selection tool allowing smart participation of solar-powered animal-mounted devices in FL training. SusFL greatly improved monitoring dependability by including a hierarchical FL design and resilience against adversarial attacks, therefore obtaining considerable advantages in energy efficiency, prediction accuracy, and system robustness. Although SusFL established significant foundations in adaptive client selection and sustainability-aware training, it was mostly limited to the optimisation of energy consumption under fixed network conditions, without specifically addressing network scalability, communication-layer efficiency, or model compression across hierarchical levels. Our current work expands on this basis by including a complete LoRaWAN-based architecture that not only supports hierarchical FL and energy-efficient model training, but also presents a new collision-avoidance MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) [3] and knowledge distillation for model compression and transfer. Unlike SusFL, which emphasises mostly on energy-aware scheduling, our solution promotes scalability, cross-layer optimisation, and real-time collaborative learning in heterogeneous and large-scale agricultural IoT installations. Our suggested architecture provides a strong and scalable solution for federated intelligence at the far edge by filling important gaps left by previous work using low-power wide-area connection combined with best client coordination and model transfer methods.

Moreover, using network slicing, Ossongo et al. [15] presented MOQoS in 2024, a multi-agent federated reinforcement learning (FRL) framework for optimising Quality of Service (QoS) in LoRa-based IoT networks. Aiming to lower packet collisions, improve throughput, and minimise energy use, their system dynamically allocated transmission power and spreading factor values using Deep Federated Q-Learning (DFQL). MOQoS also included a hierarchical slicing architecture based on SDN/NFV and an open-source simulation environment motivated by Lorasim, providing adaptive learning and fine-grained control for slice-specific IoT service needs. Although MOQoS is

mostly concerned with virtual network slicing and intra-slice parameter adjustment for performance improvement, its main emphasis is on using federated learning and reinforcement learning for LoRa-based QoS optimisation. Real-world deployment on limited devices in large-scale applications depends on cross-device collaborative training at the edge, model compression, and effective MAC-layer communication strategies—three factors it ignores. On the other hand, our suggested work adds to and expands on this basis by presenting a knowledge distillation-enhanced, hierarchical federated learning architecture coupled with an optimised collision-avoidance MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) [3]. Not only does this novel architecture guarantee effective model training and inference on low-power devices, but it also scales across various agricultural and livestock IoT environments, hence solving important problems like edge coordination, privacy, and adaptive communication. Our suggested approach greatly expands the range and practical influence of federated learning in LoRaWAN settings by combining cross-layer intelligence with low-overhead model transfer techniques, hence beyond what MOQoS by itself accomplishes.

Another recent effort towards addressing resource constraints in FL is the work in [20], where Li et al. suggested a Knowledge Distillation-Based Federated Fine-Tuning (KD-FFT) method. Their methodology incorporates low-rank adaptation to facilitate parameter-efficient model fine-tuning and utilises model-free FL through KD, which involves the interchange of only logits from public datasets. This approach prevents direct model sharing and minimises communication overhead. This method is validated on standard computer vision datasets (CIFAR-10 and SVHN), supports heterogeneous model architectures, and enhances data privacy. It exhibits good performance under non-IID conditions and significantly lower communication and storage costs in comparison to baselines such as FedAvg and FedPEFT. Nevertheless, the KD-FFT framework is constructed in a network-agnostic manner, presuming that the connections are both high-bandwidth and stable. It does not account for the communication constraints, energy limitations, or duty cycle regulations that are inherent in real-world LoRaWAN deployments. Furthermore, it functions under centralised coordination and lacks an explicit architecture for distributed model aggregation across peripheral hierarchies or multi-hop networks. In contrast, our work introduces a comprehensive, architecture-centric framework that is specifically designed for LoRaWAN, a low-power wide-area network that is constrained by severe bandwidth and energy constraints. We integrate hierarchical FL, Knowledge Distillation for lightweight model propagation, and a custom MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) that is specifically designed to mitigate packet collisions and adhere to the regulatory constraints of LoRaWAN. Our system, in contrast to previous methods, such as KD-FFT, facilitates energy-aware, scalable, and distributed FL in realistic IoT scenarios, including smart agriculture and livestock monitoring.

TABLE 1. Comparison of related works in LoRaWAN-FL systems.

Related Works Aspects						
Study	Use of FL	Communication Medium	Model Compression	MAC Optimisation	Target Application	Addresses Gaps
Kumari et al. [16]	No	LoRa	Yes (Knowledge Distillation (KD))	No	Transportation	No FL or scalable coordination
Aggarwal et al. [14]	Yes (standard asynchronous FL)	LoRaWAN	Yes (Model pruning and PCA)	Yes (asynchronous MAC)	Healthcare (ECG)	No hierarchical FL or KD integration
Miquel et al. [17]	Yes (local FL on mesh LoRa)	LoRa Mesh	No	No	Generic (Keyword spotting)	No FL coordination or scalability
Chen et al. [18]	Yes (hierarchical, energy-aware FL)	LoRaWAN	No	No	Smart Agriculture	No MAC optimization or KD
Ossongo et al. [15]	Yes (multi-agent FL with DRL)	LoRa and SDN/NFV	No	Yes (via QoS slicing)	QoS for IoT slices	No KD or hierarchical model sharing
Jindal et al. [19]	No (focus on DL inference on edge)	LoRaWAN	No (uses down-sampling of data instead)	No	Object detection (edge AI)	No FL, no scalable learning coordination
Kumar et al. [13]	Yes (FL with noisy label handling)	LoRaWAN	No	No	Transportation (ITS)	No KD or MAC-layer optimisation
Li et al. [20]	Yes (model-free FL with KD)	Network-agnostic	Yes (Low-Rank Adaptation + Knowledge Distillation)	No	Image classification (SVHN, CIFAR-10)	No MAC-layer support or network-specific integration
Proposed Work	Yes (hierarchical, edge-oriented FL)	LoRaWAN (optimised with FCA-LoRa)	Yes (Knowledge Distillation for model transfer)	Yes (FCA-LoRa for collision avoidance)	Smart Agriculture and Livestock	All the above

Table 1 reviews prior works alongside our proposed system, focussing on their usage of federated learning, communication techniques, model compression approaches, MAC-layer optimisation, application areas, and current restrictions. While others like Aggarwal et al., Miquel et al., and Chen et al. use it but with different scopes, from asynchronous communication to energy-aware or mesh-based configurations, other previous studies such as those by Kumari et al. and Jindal et al. do not use federated learning. Most previous studies lack or have little model compression or knowledge distillation; only a handful use pruning or simple KD methods. Notably, the work by Li et al. proposes a knowledge distillation-based federated fine-tuning framework that combines low-rank-adaptation-based parameter-efficient training with logit-based model-free FL, effectively reducing communication and storage overhead. However, their approach is network-agnostic, assuming stable communication environments, and does not address the MAC-layer challenges or architectural requirements of constrained IoT networks such as LoRaWAN. MAC-layer optimisations are handled in Ossongo et al. with QoS slicing and in Aggarwal et al. with asynchronous MAC design in a restricted way. By contrast, our suggested system efficiently fills the gaps in scalability, edge-device coordination, communication efficiency, and practical relevance in smart agriculture and livestock monitoring by combining hierarchical FL, knowledge distillation for quick model transfer, and an optimised MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa).

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

A. A FAIR AND RELIABLE LoRaWAN FRAMEWORK

Designed for low-power wide-area networks (LPWANs), LoRaWAN lays out the protocols and operational architecture for devices with limited resources [21], [22]. Multiple sensor nodes, also called end nodes, are typically set up in a LoRaWAN configuration to transmit data packets to a gateway. The standard components of a node include several sensors, a LoRa transceiver for signal transmission, and, if envisioned, a microcontroller. Gateways, capable of encompassing areas of hundreds of square kilometres, transmit the data they acquire to a network server using a backhaul network, such as 4G or Ethernet. Through a Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol connection, an application server talks to the network server.

Using session keys produced from the device’s root keys, LoRaWAN employs symmetric cryptography to guarantee data privacy in radio connections. The physical layer of LoRa employs a spread spectrum modulation technology that encodes data using frequency chirps that change linearly over time. The MAC layer in LoRa delineates the method by which end devices access the wireless channel for communication with gateways. LoRaWAN employs an ALOHA-based MAC protocol, hence streamlining the functionality of end devices [23]. This protocol enables end devices to communicate data to the gateway at their convenience, thus simplifying the communication process.

The FCA-LoRa scheme [3] is an enhancement of LoRaWAN that can effectively manage LoRaWAN uplink

and downlink broadcasts while encouraging scalability, high channel utilisation, and dependability. The innovative scheduling mechanism in FCA-LoRa depends on the transmission of beacon frames by the LoRa gateway to coordinate communication with end devices and improve channel efficiency through the utilisation of diverse spreading factors (SFs).

LoRa end-devices synchronise their internal clocks by receiving the latest beacon transmitted by the gateways. These beacons enable the nodes to select from multiple SF values for communication, hence increasing the probability of successful receipt at the gateway. FCA-LoRa employs a duty-cycle-aware scheduling approach, guaranteeing that nodes adhere to duty cycle limitations, such as the 1% threshold in the EU863–870 MHz ISM Band in Europe, to maximise the use of each channel [24].

FCA-LoRa utilises a modified carrier-sense multiple access with collision avoidance (CSMA/CA) model to overcome the restrictions of the ALOHA protocol in channel access. This approach employs the Listen Before Talk (LBT) methodology, wherein LoRa nodes monitor the channel for activity prior to transmission. In the revised version, nodes establish a random time offset during which they monitor the channel prior to initiating a broadcast. In the absence of channel activity during this interval, the node initiates transmission. This approach may marginally elevate energy consumption, although it substantially decreases collisions, resulting in net energy savings.

B. HIERARCHICAL FEDERATED LoRaWAN ARCHITECTURE

FL [25] is a popular technique that handles the distribution, training, and aggregation of Deep Learning models across numerous edge devices [26]. Within the scope of this article, a hierarchical FL approach is adopted that involves multiple levels of aggregation, such as local aggregators and a central server. The central server selects a set of devices from different regions, each represented by a local aggregator. The local aggregators coordinate with the devices in their respective regions to train a local model using the data collected within that region. The locally trained models are then gathered by the local aggregator of each level of aggregation, i.e., in the last layer from the actual edge nodes or in the intermediate layers from each separate aggregator, and a regional model is created through aggregation. The regional models are subsequently transmitted to the central server, where a global aggregation process combines them into an updated global model. This updated model is distributed back through the hierarchy—from the central server to local aggregators and then to devices—and the process is repeated over multiple iterations. The process is visualized in Figure 1, which illustrates the multi-layered architecture of hierarchical FL, including the global server, different layers of aggregators, and edge IoT nodes.

Considering the aforementioned architecture, we can apply FL on a LoRaWAN backbone for efficient remote IoT

FIGURE 1. Architecture of a Hierarchical Federated Learning system.

intelligence. In particular, Figure 2 illustrates the application of FL on a LoRaWAN backbone for efficient remote IoT AI deployment. In this architecture, different groups of LoRa IoT devices, organized under respective LoRa gateways, collect local data and train individual models.

The LoRaWAN architecture is structured in a star topology, facilitating a direct single-hop link between the end nodes, such as the sensor nodes, and the gateway. The gateway, equipped with Internet connectivity, is tasked with transmitting data received via LoRa packets to the upper levels of the IoT application. However, a weakness of this architecture is its inability to facilitate direct communication between end nodes. Consequently, LoRaWAN is inadequate for constructing a horizontally integrated network of IoT devices.

Each LoRa gateway acts as a local data aggregator and model aggregator within its group. The trained models from the IoT sensors are forwarded to the LoRa gateway, which aggregates the models at the group level. The group models are then exchanged through the network server and passed to the global federated server for further aggregation. This hierarchical process allows efficient model updates and data exchange across various IoT groups, while reducing the need for raw data transmission, thereby preserving data privacy

FIGURE 2. Integrated Federated LoRaWAN Architecture.

and minimizing bandwidth usage. Figure 2 also highlights the different layers: the IoT device layer, data aggregation layer, and the global federated learning layer, showing how information flows from individual sensors all the way up to the global model and then back to the devices.

LoRa is a prevalent wireless communication technology utilised in IoT applications. By utilising LoRaWAN for long-range, low-power communications, secure transmission of model updates from devices to the central server is enabled while safeguarding sensitive data. Furthermore, LoRaWAN can provide enhanced energy efficiency and prolonged battery longevity of IoT devices that are proven essential in contexts requiring years of operation without regular battery replacements, such as in agriculture (e.g., soil monitoring) or distant infrastructure surveillance. In addition, such an integrated system may efficiently scale to accommodate numerous devices, facilitating extensive IoT implementations in domains such as smart cities, where a substantial number of sensors must collaborate on learning tasks (e.g., traffic control or environmental monitoring). However, the combination of these technologies can offer enhanced system reliability, particularly in remote or adverse conditions characterized by limited network infrastructure or anticipated intermittent device connectivity (e.g., environmental monitoring in rural regions).

C. OPTIMISING THE ARCHITECTURE FOR EFFICIENT LoRa-FL MODEL PROPAGATION

1) FCA-LoRa SCHEME FOR COLLISION-LESS MODEL COMMUNICATION

In the premise of the proposed system, the FCA-LoRa scheme [3] is employed to streamline the training process and facilitate data collection from the LoRa IoT sensor nodes. Based on FCA-LoRa, each LoRa gateway disseminates beacons across several channels during a designated time frame known as the Gateway Cycle (GWDC). At each

GWDC, all gateways transmit their beacons across all accessible channels, enabling LoRa nodes within the suitable range to receive the beacons irrespective of the channel they are monitoring. These beacons furnish the scheduling information that nodes utilise to broadcast their data across the same channel from where the most recent beacon was received.

Within this framework, each gateway employs a distinct SF for beacon broadcast, followed by a super-frame, hence enhancing the probability of successful reception and optimising channel utilisation. As depicted in Figure 3, in a superframe, beacon frames are succeeded by a Beacon Period (BP), which is defined as the gap between the commencement of two consecutive beacons. Similar to traditional LoRaWAN, LoRa gateways oversee the connecting procedure of LoRa nodes. Upon receiving its initial beacon, a LoRa node transmits a join request to the gateway, which subsequently answers and broadcasts the subsequent beacon to the designated channel. The scheduling mechanism in LoRa guarantees that all channels are organised and allocated equitably, maintaining a balance in the selection of spreading factors. This leads to improved network dependability, as many data frames can arrive at their destinations concurrently. There exists a trade-off between reliability and energy consumption, as elevated SF values necessitate increased energy for prolonged transmissions.

Moreover, the employment of the enhanced CSMA-CA model in FCA-LoRa enhances the likelihood of successful transmission during the Beacon Period (BP) of a super-frame, even amongst simultaneous transmission attempts by several nodes. Prior to each transmission, an assessment is conducted regarding the probability of successfully reaching the gateway. If the transmission is anticipated to exceed the bandwidth (BW) of the current superframe, it is annulled, and the device awaits the subsequent signal to attempt again. The design of FCA-LoRa specifically tackled CSMA-CA's

FIGURE 3. Channel utilisation in FCA-LoRa scheme with 3 gateways.

vulnerability to delays. The introduction of a randomised channel sensing offset and restriction of transmissions to time slots that can be completed within defined superframe windows ensured that delays do not lead to repeated transmission failures or excessive energy consumption. Furthermore, by removing acknowledgements and regulating retry efforts, the system avoids the timing challenges commonly linked to CSMA-CA in long-range, delay-sensitive networks such as LoRaWAN. This way excessive delay propagation is mitigated and prompt and efficient communication without overflowing the channel is guaranteed. Multiple transmissions may transpire within the same bandwidth, and end devices are capable of transmitting multiple times within this interval. The suggested scheduling method minimises acknowledgement requirements, as gateways nearly always successfully receive transmitted packets, hence considerably reducing collisions.

FCA-LoRa seeks to enhance equity and optimise LoRaWAN throughput by implementing systematic bandwidth allocation, utilising the network’s scalability while reducing collisions at gateway receivers. The implementation of time slots and superframes for packet transmissions guarantees equity by providing each node an equal chance to access the channel while also considering waiting periods. This equity is upheld by ensuring that all nodes possessing data to transmit have an equal allocation of channel resources. FCA-LoRa prioritises the efficient management of network resources, guaranteeing that no transmission opportunities are squandered. Ultimately, FCA-LoRa mandates equitable channel use via GWDCs. Channel fairness guarantees that LoRaWAN packets utilise an equitable duration across each channel, hence enhancing network performance.

2) AI MODEL KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION FOR COMMUNICATION EFFICIENT MODELS

To further optimize the performance of the LoRa network and enhance model transfer efficiency, KD can be integrated

FIGURE 4. Knowledge distillation architecture.

to create lightweight AI models. The concept of KD [27] centers on a form of Model Personalization aimed at enabling knowledge transfer between two models. The model whose knowledge is distilled is called the “teacher” and is typically larger and more complex, The model that receives the knowledge is called the “student”. The process is illustrated in Figure 4. The distillation procedure involves extracting diverse forms of knowledge from different sections of the teacher model.

By employing knowledge distillation in conjunction with the LoRa protocol, it is possible to develop AI models that are more suitable for the resource-constrained environment of the LoRa network. These lightweight models will reduce the computational and bandwidth requirements for model transfers, allowing for faster and more energy-efficient communication between nodes and gateways. KD is employed at the local model training of the FL process, leveraging a bigger model to accumulate the data (teacher) and then distill it to the smaller model (student) before federation. This way the FL is done with the lightweight model while the optimisation process is done locally with the more heavyweight one. This approach not only enhances the scalability of the LoRaWAN network but also ensures that AI models can be deployed effectively in remote and decentralised applications where resources are limited.

IV. FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

While presenting the theoretical underpinning of this resource efficient LoRa-supported Hierarchical Federated framework is the basis of the paradigm, what happens when it is applied to real-world applications?

To validate this design and implementation it is important to apply its principles in a realistic scenario and quantify its interactions, either through simulation or actual deployment. To this end, this article has created a collection of case studies for the whole system and its parts.

A. REAL-WORLD APPLICATIONS

To validate the produced system, two representative real-world application domains where chosen, namely,

i) Smart Agriculture and ii) Smart Livestock Farming. Each of these scenarios is described by innate characteristics and limitations that make the application of both LoRa and FL a feasible solution for deploying AI on the edge.

Smart Agricultural and Smart Livestock monitoring serve as suitable pilot cases for assessing the proposed approach, as they represent the real-world, resource-constrained, and dispersed environments that the architecture aims to accommodate. These domains encompass geographically distributed sensing nodes, constrained power spending plans, low-bandwidth communication routes, and the necessity for continuous, localised intelligence, all of which closely correspond to the difficulties the study seeks to tackle.

In precision agriculture, equipment is frequently utilised across extensive fields with minimal infrastructure. These sensors track environmental parameters such as soil moisture, temperature, or humidity and must transmit data over extensive distances without depending on energy-intensive cellular or Wi-Fi networks. In analogous smart livestock systems, wearable or ambient sensors monitor animal movement, behaviour, or health status, frequently in remote, off-grid environments. Both use cases require solutions that are energy-efficient, low-maintenance, and able to process and transmit only the most pertinent information.

The proposed solution is distinguished by its effective alignment with these restrictions through a mix of technologies. The utilisation of LoRaWAN facilitates long-range, energy-efficient communication, which is optimal for sparsely distributed sensors. The integration of hierarchical federated learning enables edge nodes to collaboratively train models while maintaining the confidentiality of sensitive or extensive data, hence safeguarding privacy and minimising bandwidth consumption. Third, KD facilitates the implementation of lightweight models on low-power nodes, guaranteeing real-time intelligence without computational strain. The FCA-LoRa MAC protocol enhances channel access in densely populated environments, reducing collisions and augmenting data throughput—essential when numerous devices function within the same communication range.

Consequently, these scenarios not only affirm the system’s theoretical advantages but also reveal its exposure to actual operational challenges, like intermittent connection, energy constraints, and hardware heterogeneity. The effective implementation of the suggested architecture in these situations underscores its scalability, efficiency, and adaptability, hence affirming its potential for wider IoT applications in analogous restricted settings.

1) SMART AGRICULTURE

Our proposed approach leverages a fair and reliable LoRaWAN framework integrated with FL to optimize data collection and processing for efficient IoT edge intelligence. Analysing the scenario of Smart Agriculture, based on Figure 5, we have a testbed of various typologies of decentralised agricultural installations in separate locations.

FIGURE 5. Real-world examples.

Each location has a number of edge nodes that are in actuality unmanned aerial/terrestrial vehicles (UATVs) that undertake the caring of the crops. The UATVs are equipped with onboard sensors that monitor the crops in their field of responsibility.

Our current dataset contains approximately three million records from six UATV nodes in agricultural locations. Air humidity, air pressure, air temperature, soil temperature, and volumetric water content are measured. UATVs also monitor battery levels, counter data, dew point temperature, and other characteristics. This large dataset enables precise monitoring and data-driven decision-making, optimising farming efficiency.

Each UATV is equipped with an AI model for decision support, enabling the drone to manage the crop effectively. The onboard models must be optimised when crops, UATV operational conditions, and areas of responsibility evolve. Drones operate remotely and in constant motion, complicating the transmission of data to a central node for model training. FL mitigates large data transmission, hence reducing the risk of data loss or privacy concerns. Only model updates are transmitted for FL aggregation and returned to each drone to continue operations.

This approach, paired with the FCA-LoRa scheme, synchronizes communication, enhancing reliability and minimizing data collisions [3]. The role of UAVs in LoRa communication networks is a subject of scholarly interest. This paradigm enables gearbox ranges exceeding 15 km while preserving battery longevity. Both attributes are essential for real-time IoT networks in remote or inaccessible regions. LoRa communication networks are noteworthy for industrial IoT because of their resilience. [28]. The local models trained at the edge level are aggregated at local gateways and further sent for global aggregation, making it possible to:

- Develop best practices for farming by identifying weaknesses and providing actionable predictions for better decision-making.

- Set guidelines and metrics for optimal food quality and agricultural conditions by training models on diverse datasets.
- Boost farm production through AI-driven strategies for sustainability, productivity, and risk management.

FL utilising LoRaWAN enhances the global model by including local model data to improve decision-making, hence improving the entire agricultural infrastructure. Decentralised agricultural systems employ remote sensors to predict field conditions, aiming to assist farmers in maximising crop yield and minimising expenses.

2) SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING

In this domain, the proposed hierarchical FL approach integrated with a fair and reliable LoRaWAN framework allows the efficient collection and processing of data from animal care infrastructures. In particular in this real-world test scenario we have a testbed of a variety of remote livestock care units, continuously producing information about the living conditions of the animals with deployed IoT sensors in each care unit. In this setup, our dataset contains over 80,000 records collected from five different nodes deployed in the livestock care units. These records monitor environmental conditions like air humidity, air temperature, and gas concentrations such as methane (CH₄) and CO₂ levels, with methane (CH₄) as the target feature. This rich dataset supports the optimization of real-time interventions in the care units, ensuring that environmental controls are adjusted to maintain optimal living conditions for the animals, ultimately safeguarding their health and welfare.

Here, LoRaWAN serves as the communication backbone, utilizing its long-range, low-power characteristics to connect distributed sensors monitoring various parameters of livestock well-being. Each unit is equipped with an AI model that is leveraged for real-time decision making and actuation inside each facility. FL ensures that data privacy is maintained by training models locally at each edge node before aggregating them at the local gateways, similar to the smart agriculture approach. The FCA-LoRa scheme is employed to improve the reliability of the communication between nodes and gateways, thereby enhancing the accuracy of aggregated models. This distributed learning system enables:

- Develop best practices for livestock by identifying weaknesses and providing predictive insights for better decision-making.
- Set guidelines and metrics for optimal animal behavior, health, and nutrition using models trained on diverse data.
- Improve livestock production with AI-driven strategies for sustainability, productivity, and animal welfare.

By leveraging the hierarchical FL architecture over a LoRaWAN backbone, decision support systems can be improved using the collective knowledge of local models to update the global model. This enhances the overall efficiency

of livestock farming, even in remote or rural settings where network infrastructure might be limited.

B. UNPACKING THE FINDINGS: A DIVE INTO EVALUATION AND INSIGHTS

Upon examining the implementation of the suggested private-by-design Federated LoRaWAN architecture in the above practical applications, it is evident from Figures 8 and 9 that the utilisation of KD can successfully decrease the model size for transmission via LoRaWAN, resulting in enhanced throughput. In particular, the proposed approach leverages KD to facilitate model transfer and evaluates the performance of a more complex, high-capacity teacher model in contrast to a simpler, more efficient student model. The Teacher Model is generally a more complex and expressive neural network. It acquires intricate feature representations from varied data consolidated using FL. Its size and processing requirements render it unsuitable for implementation on end devices such as sensor nodes or wearables. On the other hand, the Student Model is a simplified, efficient neural network intended for deployment on resource-limited edge devices. It is trained not on raw data, but by emulating the soft predictions (e.g., probability distributions) produced by the Teacher Model, enabling it to replicate the Teacher's behaviour with many fewer parameters. The two models fundamentally differ in size and complexity. The Student Model is more suitable for implementation on LoRa-connected edge devices due to its reduced memory consumption, lower computing requirements, and less communication overhead, which coincide with the low-energy, low-bandwidth limits of LPWAN contexts. The Teacher approach, although more precise, is impracticable at these goals but provides a rich reservoir of distilled knowledge.

For the purpose of verifying the aforementioned statements, six simulated scenarios of 5, 15, 25, 35, 50, and 100 nodes respectively were conducted in OMNeT++ [29] discrete event simulator by using the FLoRa (Framework for LoRa) simulation tool [30] and the INET framework [31]. Its modular architecture, versatility in modelling network protocols, and suitability for realistically simulating wireless communication systems such LoRaWAN led to the choice of OMNeT++ as the simulation tool. Its extensibility and complex event-driven engine made it particularly suitable for the execution and evaluation of the tailored FCA-LoRa MAC protocol, where precise control over timing, collisions, and network dynamics is essential. FLoRa is an open-source implementation supporting several LoRaWAN network modules, including the LoRa physical layer and the legacy LoRaWAN MAC protocol operations. In addition, FLoRa offers a module to define the energy use of LoRa end devices. FCA-LoRa was implemented by programming the physical, MAC, and application layers in FLoRa from the very beginning, as described in detail in [3]. A topology simulation diagram in Figure 6 helps to highlight the fundamental networking elements of a LoRaWAN network

FIGURE 6. Topology diagram of the LoRa Network in OMNeT++.

that can support FL model exchange and on which the FCA-LoRa scheme was implemented.

In the experimental scenarios, it was assumed that LoRa IoT nodes were randomly allocated throughout a wide deployment area. The nodes were set to communicate with seven distinct LoRa gateways, which served as FL aggregators, to facilitate the FL model training process. This was accomplished via the exchange of data packets that signified the model updates during the training phase. The simulation parameters utilised are depicted in summary in Table 2.

These experimental scenarios highlight the critical role of utilising lightweight models, such as the Student Model, instead of heavier models, like the Teacher Model, in the execution of the FL process within a LoRa-based network. Figure 7 presents the dataflow algorithm of the proposed architecture to be evaluated. It defines each step from the acquisition of local sensor data and model training to gateway-level aggregation, inter-gateway synchronisation, and the ultimate dissemination of the global model, all in accordance with the federated learning lifecycle and LoRaWAN limitations.

The principal objective of the proposed integrated Federated LoRaWAN architecture is to combine the strengths of both IoT networking protocols and AI to attain seamless interoperability. The FL models employed in these experiments were designed and developed using datasets obtained from the Smart Agriculture and Smart Livestock Farming scenarios, as described in the previous section, hence confirming their applicability to real-world IoT applications. The two experimental scenarios for Smart Agriculture and Smart Livestock Monitoring were executed with identical network configurations and communication parameters to maintain consistency in assessing the system's performance. The difference between the two scenarios resides in the type of data collected, which embodies the specific attributes of each application. In Smart Agriculture, data is derived by static, uniformly dispersed sensors that monitor environmental conditions over extensive areas, whereas in the

TABLE 2. Simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value
Deployment Area	5000x5000 meters
Number of Gateways	7
Channel Bandwidth	125kHz
Radio Channels	9
Data SF value	7 to 12
Beacon SF value	12
Duty Cycle	≤1%
Code Rate	4/5
Max Transmission Power	14 dBm
Beacon Window	128 sec
Avg Packet Rate	2 minutes

Smart Livestock Monitoring setting, data is produced by mobile, animal-mounted sensors that capture behavioural information. The variation in data sources facilitated the evaluation of FCA-LoRa's efficacy across several real-world applications, illustrating its ability to accommodate both stationary and dynamic sensing contexts within a cohesive simulation framework.

In the context of the LoRa data transmission utilised in this study, data size is particularly crucial, as numerous countries globally impose duty cycle restrictions that limit the number of bytes a LoRa node can broadcast during a specified timeframe. Nevertheless, the timeframe for transmitting sensor data may be extended to attain a low bit rate and steady connectivity. The maximum payload size of an FCA-LoRa packet is restricted to 222 bytes. We consider that nine channels are accessible according to the European regional specifications for LoRa nodes transmitting data packets to the gateways [32], [33]. Each channel is organised into units of superframes, which possess a defined structure and duration as described in [3].

The channel bandwidth and coding rate are set at 125 kHz and 4/5, respectively. The transmission power was configured at 14dBm, with SFs varying from 7 to 12. FCA-LoRa specifies that for a signal to be effectively received, its reception power should be more than the sensitivity of the receiver. The transmitter's transmission power, as well as losses brought on by signal distortion and shadowing, affect the reception power of the signal. In light of this, the radio channel was modelled with shadowing using a path loss model suitable for long-distance LoRa transmissions [3]. This model additionally includes Gaussian-distributed shadowing effects to account for environmental variability, therefore calculating the received signal strength based on the transmitter's power, the path loss over a reference distance, and a log-distance path loss exponent. The formula used is as follows:

$$P_{Loss}(dis) = \overline{P_{Loss}(dis_0)} + 10 \log\left(\frac{dis}{dis_0}\right) + G \quad (1)$$

where dis is the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, $P_{Loss}(dis_0)$ is the mean path loss for dis_0 , α is the path loss exponent, and G is a zero-mean Gaussian distributed random variable with standard deviation. Reflecting variations caused by obstacles, terrain, and other interference

FIGURE 7. Dataflow algorithm of the federated LoRaWAN architecture.

sources, this modelling technique offers a more accurate depiction of LoRa radio propagation in rural or large-scale settings.

Moreover, in regards to energy consumption, the analysis concentrated on observing the states of the radio transceiver, transmit, receive, and idle, for each LoRa end-device over the simulation time. The simulation model included an energy-aware module that tracked the operation of each LoRa node’s radio transceiver, differentiating among various states. The states were associated with actual current consumption numbers obtained from the Semtech SX1272/73 datasheet [34], utilising a supply voltage of 3.3 V to compute energy consumption over time. The total energy consumed by each device was calculated by aggregating the energy spent during active states, while transmitting or receiving, and during idle periods, when the device was effectively inactive.

To facilitate the transmission of FL models via LoRaWAN, each model is divided into a designated number and sequence of packets. Thus, a reduced model leads to fewer communicated packets, thereby improving transmission reliability and minimising energy consumption. The use of the FCA-LoRa scheme ensures the system’s fairness and efficiency by substantially mitigating the likelihood of collisions, regardless of the increasing number of LoRa IoT nodes.

In particular, Figure 8 depicts the throughput evaluation of the Teacher Model and the Student Model as a proportion of successfully delivered packets. The Student Model, derived from KD, has remarkable consistency, with a throughput exceeding 90% across all node counts, including 100 nodes. Conversely, throughput decreases to below 85% at 100 nodes

FIGURE 8. Throughput evaluation of model transfer utilising the LoRa-FL on real-world application data.

FIGURE 9. Packet error rate evaluation of model transfer utilising the LoRa-FL scheme.

for the Teacher Model, signifying that the utilisation of KD can leverage throughput with increased network scalability. The Teacher Model is failing to meet the expectations of larger networks regarding efficient data delivery, as evidenced by this decline. The Student Model ensures dependable communication in congested environments through its consistently high throughput, attributable to enhanced scalability and capacity to manage rising traffic demands.

The same conclusion becomes evident in Figure 9, where the Student Model and the Teacher Model exhibit significantly divergent PERs, indicating their relative ineffectiveness in maintaining transmission reliability. Even with the network comprising 100 nodes, the Student Model sustains a packet error rate below 15%. The Teacher Model exhibits a PER that rapidly escalates with rising node counts, surpassing 30% at 100 nodes. As network density escalates, the Teacher Model’s reliability diminishes due to congestion, interference, or inadequate resource allocation, evidenced by a significant rise in failures. The Student Model’s exceptional data transmission management and minimal error rates exhibit its robustness, ensuring dependability in challenging network conditions.

FIGURE 10. Number of packets sent and received for the student model transfer utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

FIGURE 12. Number of packets dropped during for the model transfers utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

FIGURE 11. Number of packets sent and received for the teacher model transfer utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

FIGURE 13. Packet load distribution in the seven gateways/aggregators for the student model transfer utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

Figure 10 illustrates the packet transmission and reception rates of the Student Model for varying node counts. The findings indicate that the Student Model is dependable; even at a network size of 100 nodes, the counts of received and sent packets are closely aligned. In a network including 100 nodes, there is minimal fluctuation in the percentage of packets transmitted by the Student Model. The reliability and minimal packet delivery loss demonstrate that the Student Model effectively accommodates increasing network demands. The Student Model is ideal for extensive implementations where reliability is paramount, evidenced by the strong correlation between transmitted and received packets.

Similarly, Figure 11 illustrates the efficacy of the Teacher Model in receiving and transmitting packets. A growing gap between the total packets transmitted and those successfully received is noted in the Teacher Model, unlike the Student Model, as the number of nodes escalates. This difference becomes increasingly evident with elevated node counts, such as 100 nodes, indicating significant packet losses [35]. According to this pattern, the Teacher Model appears to struggle with maintaining reliable packet delivery as network density increases. Poor packet handling not only diminishes the reliability of data delivery but also squanders network resources. The Teacher Model is less suitable

for dense deployments compared to the Student Model, as its performance significantly deteriorates under substantial network loads.

Supplementary, Figure 12 illustrates the performance of the models across various network settings by comparing the total number of packets dropped by each model. The Teacher Model indicates that the quantity of lost packets escalates significantly with the incorporation of nodes, surpassing 200,000 at 100 nodes. The Teacher Model’s inability to effectively manage large-scale networks results in squandered resources and diminished reliability. Conversely, even with 100 nodes, the Student Model minimises packet loss. The Student Model efficiently allocates network resources, reduces losses, and guarantees reliable communication, as evidenced by this significant disparity. The disparity between the two models underscores the Student Model’s superiority in scalability and reliability within crowded network situations.

Furthermore, Figure 13 and Figure 14 depict the allocation of packet load among seven distinct LoRa Gateways (FL aggregators) for the Student and Teacher Models as node counts increase. In particular, the figures illustrate the spatial and functional balance of network load across gateways

FIGURE 14. Packet load distribution in the seven gateways/aggregators for the teacher model transfer utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

GW1 to GW7 within the LoRa-FL scheme. Although all gateways serve a similar core role as regional aggregators that oversee data and model exchanges from proximate edge devices, they do not have functionally distinct roles regarding hierarchy or control. Their significance stems from geographical coverage and load distribution efficiency. The variation in packet load among GW1–GW7 is affected by device density, physical proximity, and channel conditions within each gateway’s service area. Certain gateways may accommodate a greater concentration of devices or possess a more central location, leading to an increased amount of student model transfers being directed through them. In contrast, gates in less populated or remote areas may demonstrate reduced load levels. The depicted balanced but non-uniform distribution demonstrates that the FCA-LoRa MAC protocol, in conjunction with hierarchical FL and KD, successfully prevents the overloading of any individual gateway, despite devices functioning asynchronously within strict duty-cycle limitations.

Regarding Figure 13 and the Student Model, at reduced node counts, such as 5 or 15, the distribution of network traffic is relatively uniform, as seen by the balanced packet load across gateways. Some gateways, such as GW1 and GW7, experience excessive strain at 100 nodes, whilst others, like GW2 and GW4, remain somewhat unencumbered. This event is attributed to the random distribution and placement of nodes in relation to the various LoRa Gateways. Despite this imbalance, the Student Model demonstrates that the load is spread in a manageable manner, hence averting scalability problems and excessive congestion at any single gateway.

Relative to the Student Model, the Teacher Model exhibits a significantly greater total load in Figure 14, which illustrates the distribution of packet load among the seven LoRa Gateways. The distribution appears to be somewhat equitable for lower node numbers, such as 5 or 15 nodes. The Teacher Model imposes a considerably greater load on gateways with 100 nodes or more. Network performance may be adversely affected by congestion and bottlenecks, as evidenced by the high traffic on some gateways. The Teacher Model is less efficient and scalable for larger deployments than the Student

FIGURE 15. Energy consumption variation for model transfers utilising the LoRA-FL scheme.

Model due to its significantly greater demand on network infrastructure.

The comparison of energy usage fluctuations across different node counts in Figure 15 clearly illustrates how the Teacher and Student models respond to increasing network demands. Figure 15 demonstrates the percentage change in energy consumption while the network escalates. The variation in energy consumption of the Teacher Model increases significantly with the number of nodes, peaking at almost 130% increase for 35 nodes before progressively declining after 50 nodes. The escalating network density indicates a significant increase in energy usage relative to the baseline. Conversely, the energy consumption pattern of the Student Model is significantly more stable, fluctuating slightly about 100% and consistently hovering near 110%. The stability of the Student Model, despite an increase in the number of nodes, illustrates its energy efficiency. According to these trends, the Teacher Model’s inefficiency increases with the size of the network, in contrast to the Student Model’s improved energy management and consistency.

The results of this experimental research highlight the efficiency of Federated Learning in LoRaWAN-based IoT settings, especially in improving scheduling approaches for optimal network performance. Rather than emphasising machine learning accuracy, this study differs from traditional Federated Learning studies in that it addresses network efficiency and the fundamental communication constraints of LoRaWAN, such limited data transfer rates, duty cycle restrictions, and energy consumption concerns. For frequent and large model updates, these restrictions create significant challenges and make the use of Federated Learning in LoRa-based IoT applications a challenging issue.

A fundamental element of the proposed architecture is the application of KD to compress complex Teacher Models into simplified Student Models appropriate for deployment on LoRa-connected IoT devices. This technique presents an essential trade-off between model compactness and maintained learning efficiency. Model compression by KD is essential for edge deployments, as resource-limited nodes cannot support the memory, compute, or energy

requirements of complete instructor models. On the other hand, diminishing model size necessarily generates concerns regarding possible decrease in inference performance.

Overall, the distinction between the Teacher and Student Models is primarily assessed based on their computational and communication efficiency within the LoRaWAN-based federated learning architecture, rather than through direct accuracy evaluations. While no specific accuracy measures are provided, the implementation of KD guarantees that the Student Model integrates the Teacher's decision-making behaviours by being approximately 15% smaller in size [36]. The qualitative evaluation demonstrates that the Student Model possess the predictive capability to function reliably in smart agricultural and livestock monitoring contexts. The architecture's efficacy depends on the notion that the student need not entirely emulate the teacher's complex complexity; rather, it encapsulates fundamental behavioural patterns via soft-target monitoring. This information transfer enables the learner to effectively generalise in real-world activities, even in the absence of direct access to raw data or centralised training.

Nonetheless, this balance has complexities. The Student Model is not anticipated to replicate the Teacher's whole representational capability. It functions within narrower margins of tolerance for variability, which may affect precision in tasks involving extremely ambiguous inputs or in edge cases inadequately represented during distillation. However, the operational advantages are significant: diminished communication payloads, decreased inference time, and enhanced energy efficiency, elements that are essential for LoRaWAN networks with stringent duty cycle limitations and restricted bandwidth. The qualitative result, then, supports the notion that minor tradeoffs in model expressiveness are required by the operational practicality and scalability achieved through compression. This facilitates the extensive and sustainable implementation of intelligent IoT applications in remote areas where power and connectivity are limited.

The system's assessment emphasises criteria such as energy consumption, communication overhead, and throughput within MAC-layer limitations, all of which indicate the system's suitability for practical, resource-limited implementations. The findings indicate that the Student Model facilitates scalable and energy-efficient intelligence at the edge, eliminating the necessity to transmit or process whole instructor models on endpoint devices. In particular, the Student Model surpassed the Teacher Model primarily due to its reduced size, a result of KD, enabling it to operate more efficiently within the limitations of the LoRaWAN framework. The Teacher Model faced significant challenges due to LoRaWAN's restricted bandwidth, duty cycle, and inadequate data transmission rate, requiring supplementary resources and increased transmission sizes. The Student Model, conversely, aligned more effectively with the LoRa-FL scheme due to its reduced size, which enhanced energy efficiency, packet delivery reliability, and scalability. These findings illustrate the necessity for FL

applications to modify model architecture in accordance with communication medium limitations.

C. OUTCOMES AND INTERPRETATIONS

The findings of this experimental study demonstrate the efficacy of FL utilising LoRa technology in real-time applications. The study does not address metrics pertinent to Federated Learning or Machine Learning accuracy [37]; instead, it focuses on evaluating the network performance of the proposed integrated Federated LoRaWAN scheme. This emphasis is essential as LoRaWAN has limitations that hinder regular and voluminous communication, which are necessary for advanced machine learning models. These constraints encompass reduced data transfer rates and duty cycle restrictions. This study adeptly utilises the KD approach to reduce the volume of data that must be transmitted, hence alleviating the constraints of LoRaWAN's limited data transmission capacity. The FCA-LoRa system also supports asynchronous model updates, hence augmenting the network's operating efficiency and reliability.

The experimental results indicate that, the Student Model surpassed the Teacher Model in the LoRa-FL framework due to several significant factors, including the distinctive attributes of the Student Model, the limitations of the LoRaWAN framework, and the experimental conditions. To facilitate an equitable comparison, both models were evaluated within an identical simulated environment featuring seven LoRa Gateways (FL aggregators), with the LoRa nodes randomly distributed. Nonetheless, the Student Model surpassed the others owing to its reduced size and its development through KD, which are two significant distinctions among the models.

The results were substantially influenced by the limitations of the LoRaWAN framework. LoRaWAN is not intended for substantial data transmissions or frequent communications because of its limited data transfer rate and strict duty cycle constraints. In FL, the Teacher Model's complexity and size required more frequent updates and larger data transfers to communicate its status. These expectations would have imposed a strain on the LoRaWAN framework, leading to higher congestion, heightened energy consumption, and a greater incidence of packet loss, especially as the number of nodes escalated. In contrast, the Student Model facilitated improved communication due to its reduced size post-KD procedure, hence using fewer transmission resources. Its compact size enabled superior compliance with LoRaWAN requirements, reducing the likelihood of packet loss and minimising power usage.

A further advantage of the Student Model is its enhanced scalability with increasing network sizes. The Teacher Model resulted in significant congestion at certain gateways within the seven-gateway simulated environment, leading to an unbalanced load distribution as the number of nodes increased. The larger size of the Teacher Model exacerbated the situation by increasing its dependence on the limited

LoRaWAN bandwidth. The smaller Student Model effectively distributed traffic more uniformly among gateways, so averting overloads resulting from these bottlenecks. The diminished model size enables more efficient management of the FCA-LoRa scheme's asynchronous updates, resulting in elevated throughput and minimal error rates.

Ultimately, in terms of network performance, the Student Model exhibited more energy efficiency than the Teacher Model. The Student Model was minimised, resulting in a reduced data volume transmitted over the network and decreased energy consumption for processing and communication. The critical significance of energy constraints for Internet of Things devices operating on constrained power sources is paramount in LoRaWAN scenarios. Energy consumption fluctuations would have been more pronounced across network sizes and larger configurations due to the Teacher Model's heightened transmission demands and higher dimensions.

To enhance network performance in FL-enabled LoRa environments, these findings underscore the significance of the proposed integrated Federated LoRaWAN scheme and methodologies, particularly the incorporation of KD and FCA-LoRa. Moreover, related works presented in Section II only partially validate the foundational assumptions of the current study. These works focus particularly in demonstrating the accuracy and feasibility of FL over LoRa networks. Studies such as [14] and [18] offer clear evidence that FL can be successfully deployed in constrained IoT environments, achieving high prediction accuracy while significantly reducing data transmission volumes and preserving privacy. These works confirm that FL, when tailored correctly, is effective in LoRa-based systems from an application-level perspective. However, the contribution of our proposed work extends beyond validating the accuracy of FL. Our work presents a comprehensive architecture-centric approach that focuses specifically on how FL models can be effectively transferred and managed over LoRaWAN, a network characterized by strict communication constraints. Unlike previous studies, our work systematically addresses the unique challenges posed by LoRaWAN, including limited data transfer rates, stringent duty cycle regulations, and energy consumption limitations, by proposing a tightly integrated framework that combines hierarchical FL, KD for model compression, and a novel MAC protocol (FCA-LoRa) designed to minimize packet collisions and manage traffic flow efficiently. While earlier studies confirm that FL is accurate and viable in LoRa contexts, they do not provide in-depth architectural solutions for enabling scalable, energy-aware model distribution and training coordination within a LoRaWAN infrastructure. Thus, the value of our study lies in filling this critical gap, offering not only empirical validation through simulation but also a blueprint for real-world deployment of intelligent, low-power IoT systems using FL over LoRaWAN.

On the other hand, the experimental findings in [3] somewhat validate and justify the results in our proposed work, especially regarding network performance, energy

consumption, and MAC-layer behaviour in LoRaWAN settings. The work in [3] focusses on the design, implementation, and simulation of the FCA-LoRa MAC protocol in OMNeT++, assessing energy consumption, collision rates, and throughput across different network densities and configurations. These findings are significantly relevant to the ones presented in the current study, which incorporates FCA-LoRa as a fundamental element of its architecture. The energy savings, enhanced channel access efficiency, and reduced packet loss demonstrated in [3] provide direct concrete proof for the claims stated in our proposed work concerning MAC-layer optimisation. The experimental findings of [3] validate the MAC-layer efficiency and communication reliability features of our work, especially highlighting the advantages of FCA-LoRa. In addition, although direct latency measurements are not presented in this study, the proposed architecture is inherently designed to reduce communication delays. Hierarchical FL aggregation decreases the number of communication rounds, knowledge distillation compresses models to reduce transmission payloads, and the FCA-LoRa MAC protocol minimizes retransmissions through effective collision avoidance. Together, these elements contribute to lower overall latency in LoRaWAN-based FL deployments. A more detailed latency analysis is planned as part of future work, particularly in real-world deployment scenarios.

Furthermore, the integrated insights from [11] and [12] offer substantial validation for the key components and assumptions of the system outlined in our proposed work, although from complementary perspectives. The work in [12] examines the application of FL in decentralised smart farming contexts utilising LSTM models. A comparative comparison of locally trained models and federated models reveals that federated learning can achieve comparable or superior prediction accuracy, especially in practical agricultural and livestock contexts. These findings clearly validate the effectiveness and applicability of FL in the specific domains addressed by our work, hence reinforcing the architectural decision to implement FL for distributed intelligence in smart agriculture and livestock monitoring.

In contrast, the work done in [11] examines the function of KD in FL systems and demonstrates how student models can be optimised and tailored across many nodes without considerable loss of accuracy. This study endorses the application of KD as a model compression technique, which is pivotal to the objectives outlined in our work aimed at diminishing the computational load and communication overhead associated with model deployment across LoRaWAN networks. By demonstrating that lightweight student models may preserve the functionality of bigger teacher models in decentralised settings, [11] offers empirical support for the KD-driven model transfer technique employed in our current study.

Collectively, these two studies affirm the fundamental ideas of our proposed approach: that FL is efficient in smart farming applications, and that KD is a feasible approach for scaling FL to resource-constrained edge devices. Although

neither research directly tackles the network-specific difficulties of LoRaWAN, their collective findings validate that the learning components of our proposed architecture, federated model training and lightweight model transfer, are robust, pragmatic, and advantageous. Consequently, they jointly enhance the significance, practicality, and performance capabilities of the proposed hierarchical FL system functioning over limited LPWAN infrastructures.

This study illustrates how advancements can address the limitations of LoRaWAN to facilitate efficient and scalable communication in IoT applications. This study is highly pertinent for applications that require reliable and energy-efficient communication infrastructure, as it emphasises network performance over Federated Learning accuracy metrics.

V. CONCLUSION

Ultimately, practical examples demonstrate that constrained edge deployments are efficiently managed through the implementation of a private-by-design Federated LoRaWAN architecture. Artificial intelligence models are improved for transmission across LoRaWAN by integrating KD, significantly reducing their size without compromising performance. Reduction in model size enhances system efficiency by improving throughput and minimizing unnecessary communication overhead. This architecture can allow lightweight, scalable, and privacy-preserving IoT intelligence at the edge, as indicated by the evaluation findings. The primary objectives of future research are to enhance KD methodologies to further mitigate model deterioration and to explore bigger real-world implementations to demonstrate the architecture's scalability in various IoT ecosystems.

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ANNA TRIANTAFYLLOU was born in Ioannina, Greece. She received the Diploma degree (5 years) from the Department of Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Greece, in 2017. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Western Macedonia. Up until now, she has published 14 papers in international journals and conferences, including *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, *Information (MDPI)*, *Computer Networks*, and *IEEE OPEN JOURNAL OF THE COMMUNICATIONS SOCIETY*. She is also a Research Associate in national and European funded research projects in the same University. More specifically, she was involved in the Operational Program DIAS: Drone Innovation in saffron Agriculture Surveillance (Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship, and Innovation); the H2020-SU-DS-2018 (SU-DS04-2018-2020), SDN-microSENSE: SDN-microgrid reSilient Electrical eNergy SystEm; and H2020-ICT-2020-1 (ICT-56-2020) TERMINET: nexT gEneRation sMart INterconnectEd IoT. Her research interests include the Internet of Things, communication protocols, and LoRaWAN. She received the Graduation Excellence Award from the Technical Chamber of Greece in 2018. She received the Award of "Best Communication Systems Paper" in the 9th International Conference on Modern Circuits and Systems Technologies (MOCASST) on Electronics and Communications 2020.

ILIAS SINIOSOGLU received the Diploma degree (5 years) from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Greece, in 2020. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the University of Western Macedonia. He is also a Research Associate with the University of Western Macedonia, in national and European funded research projects, including H2020-DS-SC7-2017 (DS-07-2017), SPEAR: Secure and PrivatE smArt gRid; H2020-SU-DS-2018 (SU-DS04-2018), SDNmicroSENSE: SDN-microgrid reSilient Electrical eNergy SystEm; MARS: sMart fArming with dRoneS (Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship, and Innovation); and H2020-ICT-2020-1 (ICT-56-2020) TERMINET: nexT gEneRation sMart INterconnectEd IoT. His research interests include deep and federated learning on next generation IoT platforms, primarily focusing on optimization, deployment, and scalability methodologies.

VASILEIOS ARGYRIOU (Member, IEEE) received the B.Sc. degree in computer science from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, in 2001, and the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering working on registration from the University of Surrey, in 2003 and 2006, respectively. From 2001 to 2002, he held a research position with the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, working on image and video watermarking. He joined the Communications and Signal Processing Department, Imperial College London, London, in 2007, where he was a Research Fellow working on 3D object reconstruction. He is currently a Professor with Kingston University London, working on computer vision and AI for crowd and human behavior analysis, computer games, entertainment, and medical applications. Also, research is conducted on educational games and on HCI for augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) systems.

SOTIRIOS K. GOUDOS (Senior Member, IEEE) received the B.Sc. degree in physics, the M.Sc. degree in electronics, and the Ph.D. degree in physics from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece, in 1991, 1994, and 2001, respectively, the M.Sc. degree in information systems from the University of Macedonia, Greece, in 2005, and the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, in 2011.

He is currently a Professor with the Department of Physics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. He is the Director of the ELEDIA@AUTH Laboratory and a member with the ELEDIA Research Center Network. He has authored the book *Emerging Evolutionary Algorithms for Antennas and Wireless Communications* (Institution of Engineering and Technology, 2021). His research interests include antenna and microwave structure design, evolutionary algorithms, wireless communications, machine learning, and semantic web technologies. He has participated as a guest editor or lead a guest editor in several special issues in international journals. He has co-organized special sessions at international conferences. He is serving as the Chapter/AG Coordinator for the IEEE Greece Section. He has been elected IEEE Greece Section Secretary for 2022 and the IEEE Greece Section Vice-Chair for 2023–2024 and 2025–2026. He is the Founding Editor-in-Chief of the *Telecom* (MDPI). He is also serving as an Associate Editor for *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON ANTENNAS AND PROPAGATION*, *IEEE ACCESS*, and *IEEE OPEN JOURNAL OF THE COMMUNICATIONS SOCIETY*.

GEORGIOS TH. PAPAPOPOULOS (Member, IEEE) received the M.Eng. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, in 2005 and 2011, respectively. He is currently an Assistant Professor with the Department of Informatics and Telematics, Harokopio University of Athens, Greece. He has more than 80 publications in international academic conferences and scientific journals. He has over 20 years of experience in participating in EU-funded R&I projects in the areas of ICT, security, and robotics. His research interests include computer vision, machine/deep learning, and artificial intelligence. He is a member of the Technical Chamber of Greece.

KONSTANTINOS PANITSIDIS was a Lecturer with Democritus University and the University of Western Macedonia, in the field of informatics of Thrace. He is currently an Assistant Professor with the Department of Management Science and Technology, University of Western Macedonia, in “development, planning and programming of applications in decision making.” He has 15 years of professional experience as an IT by participating in research and development programs, funded by European Union and National Resources, with a variety of responsibilities mainly focused on the development of integrated environmental technology, IT solutions, and the provision of specialized consulting services related to environmental issues. He has published more than ten scientific papers in international journals and conferences. His research interests include decision support systems, data science, green technologies, virtual reality, geoinformatics, natural resource management, sustainable development, databases, geographic information systems, knowledge mining, information systems, and application development.

PANAGIOTIS SARIGIANNIDIS (Member, IEEE) received the B.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in computer science from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece, in 2001 and 2007, respectively. He is currently the Director of the ITHACA Laboratory, the Co-Founder of the 1st spin-off of the University of Western Macedonia: MetaMind Innovations P.C., and an Associate Professor with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of

Western Macedonia, Kozani, Greece. He has published more than 260 papers in international journals, conferences, and book chapters, including IEEE COMMUNICATIONS SURVEYS AND TUTORIALS, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON COMMUNICATIONS, IEEE INTERNET OF THINGS JOURNAL, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON BROADCASTING, IEEE SYSTEMS JOURNAL, IEEE *Wireless Communications Magazine*, IEEE OPEN JOURNAL OF THE COMMUNICATIONS SOCIETY, IEEE/OSA JOURNAL OF LIGHTWAVE TECHNOLOGY, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INDUSTRIAL INFORMATICS, IEEE ACCESS, and *Computer Networks*. He has been involved in several national, European, and international projects. He is currently the project coordinator of three H2020 Projects, namely H2020-DS-SC7-2017 (DS-07-2017), SPEAR: Secure and PrivatE smArt gRid; H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-1 (LC-SC3-EC4-2020), EVIDENT: bEhavioral Insights and Effective eNergy policy acTions; and H2020-ICT-2020-1 (ICT-56-2020), TERMINET: nexT gEneRation sMART InterconnectEd IoT, while he coordinates the Operational Program MARS: sMART fArming with dRoneS (Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship, and Innovation) and the Erasmus+ KA2 ARRANGE-ICT: SmartROOT: Smart faRming innOvatiOn Training. He also serves as a Principal Investigator for the H2020-SUDS-2018 (SU-DS04-2018), SDN-microSENSE: SDN-microgrid reSilient Electrical eNergy SystEm and in three Erasmus+ KA2: ARRANGE-ICT: pArtneRship foR AddressiNG mEgatrends in ICT, JAUNTY: Joint undergAduate coUrseS for smart eNergy management sYstems, and STRONG: advanced firST ResPONDers traininG (Cooperation for Innovation and the Exchange of Good Practices). His research interests include telecommunication networks, the Internet of Things, and network security. He participates on the editorial boards of various journals.

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